

REMOTE MONITORING OF WATER SURFACE POLLUTION

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Abstract: Remote sensing is a method that enables efficient and cost-effective monitoring of large and inaccessible areas. Remote sensing plays a significant role in detecting and analyzing pollutants present on the surface of water. Special emphasis in this paper is placed on the satellite missions SMOS, Aquarius/SAC-D, and GRACE, which were developed to monitor ocean salinity, soil moisture, changes in ocean circulation, and shifts in Earth's mass distribution. The paper also presents specific examples of water pollution detected through remote sensing. Examples include the environmental crisis in the Gulf of Mexico caused by the Deepwater Horizon oil rig explosion and an oil spill in a river near Norilsk, Russia. Satellite imagery allowed for precise tracking of the extent and impact of these events on the environment. The paper also demonstrates how digital images can be further enhanced using software tools, contributing to better interpretation and visualization of data.

Keywords: Remote sensing, SMOS, Aquarius/SAC-D, GRACE.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the today's era of climate change and growing human influence on natural resources, monitoring the state of water bodies has become a key task in environmental protection (Rice, 2023). Remote sensing, as a method of collecting data without direct contact with the observed objects, enables continuous and comprehensive monitoring of large water surfaces, including seas, oceans, lakes, and rivers. Through the application of satellite missions including SMOS (Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity), Aquarius/SAC-D, and GRACE (Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment), data are collected on parameters like salinity, soil moisture, gravitational variability, and other indicators that enable the analysis of hydrological processes and potential sources of pollution (Dione & Faye, 2024). The purpose of this paper is to highlight the significance, capabilities, and applications of remote sensing in both ecological and scientific contexts, with a particular focus on specific examples and technologies used for monitoring the quality and changes of water resources around the world.

2. REMOTE SENSING OF THE STATE OF WATER BODIES

At the beginning of 1998, parallel efforts in Europe and the United States were directed toward exploring the concept of satellite sensors and mission design for measuring salinity as either a secondary or primary objective. Several campaigns were initiated to obtain new data and evaluate the models. Two research missions were approved: the SMOS and the Aquarius/SAC-D (Vernières et al., 2014).

2.1. SMOS mission

The research mission of the European Space Agency (ESA) is dedicated to enabling global observation of land surface soil moisture and ocean salinity (Weng, 2011). The SMOS satellite helps to clarify how the Earth's surface and atmosphere interact, supporting improvements in environmental prediction models (Bajjou Mroczkowska, 2018). The SMOS satellite was launched on November 2, 2009, and although it was

originally designed as a five-year mission, it has been extended, reflecting its versatility and new synergistic capabilities (European Space Agency, n.d.). The appearance of the SMOS satellite in orbit is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Satellite in orbit (European Space Agency, n.d.)

The SMOS satellite is equipped innovative interferometric radiometer that operates within the L-band microwave spectrum, allowing for accurate temperature observations. This data is used to produce a global soil moisture map every three days. (United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs, n.d.).

SMOS enables the monitoring of changes related to the amount of water present in the surface layers of soil and the concentration of salt in the upper layer of the sea. Figure 2 shows the average distribution of salinity in seas and oceans. Areas shown in red indicate high salinity levels, while green represents low salinity levels. The figure also displays a simplified global pattern of ocean circulation known as thermohaline circulation. Blue arrows are used to show cold deep currents, and red arrows depict warm surface currents (Sheldon et al., 2016).

Figure 2: Sea and Ocean Salinity and Global Circulation (European Space Agency, n.d.)

2.2. AQUARIUS/SAC-D mission

NASA and CONAE partnered to develop the Aquarius/SAC-D mission. Figure 3 illustrates the design of the Aquarius/SAC-D spacecraft (Le Vine, Jacob, Dinnat, de Matthaeis, & Abraham, 2007).

Figure 3: Aquarius/SAC-D spacecraft (Le Vine, Dinnat, Meissner, & Wentz, 2018)

The mission was launched on June 10, 2011, and concluded on June 8, 2015. SAC-D/Aquarius is a multi-sensor mission that covers the ocean, land, atmosphere, and space. Its main aim is to enhance to the understanding of the Earth's system (Sen, Caruso, & Lagerloef, 2008). The primary scientific objective is to examine the mechanisms that lead to changes in the water cycle and ocean circulation, as well as their impact on climate, by measuring global variations in sea surface salinity. Additional objectives include: observing environmental changes, natural hazards, and sea ice (Lagerloef & Torrusio, 2008).

Through measurements of ocean salinity variations, Aquarius/SAC-D contributed valuable data. Salinity, along with temperature, determines how dense and buoyant seawater is. This, in turn, provides information about the ocean water layers and how they mix.

2.3. GRACE mission

GRACE is a geodetic mission of the United States and Germany. Its overall goal is to obtain long-term, precise data on on both the average levels and the changing elements of Earth's gravitational field (European Space Agency, n.d.). The appearance of the GRACE satellite is shown in Figure 4.

Some of the scientific objectives are: to study ocean currents and heat flow, monitor seafloor pressure and track changes in ice sheets, land water storage and glaciers. (Tapley, Bettadpur, Watkins, & Reigber, 2004).

Figure 4: GRACE satellite (Zurich, 2025)

The mission concept is based on measuring variations in the distance among two coplanar satellites and their derivatives (Prost, 2025). The orbits of the two separate spacecraft vary as they pass through Earth's gravitational field, resulting in measurable variations between them. The GRACE satellites were launched into Earth orbit on March 17, 2002, and operated for three times longer than originally planned - until the launch of the new GRACE-2 satellites on October 27, 2017 (NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory, n.d.).

3. EXAMPLES OF REMOTE SENSING OF WATER SURFACE POLLUTION

The use of satellite imagery is possible in all phases of environmental research, which requires the application of multiple methodological approaches, including both remote sensing and terrestrial investigations (Regodić, Sekulović, & Živković, 2010).

3.1. Disaster in the Gulf of Mexico

On April 20, 2010, a major environmental disaster occurred at the Deepwater Horizon oil rig in the Gulf of Mexico (Figure 5). The Deepwater Horizon oil spill, one of the largest marine oil disasters in history, polluted more than a thousand kilometers of Louisiana's marshy coastline, posing a severe threat to the local ecosystem (Bukharitsin, 2022).

After the explosion on the platform, crude oil began leaking into the sea from its well, located 1,500 meters below the ocean surface. The greatest victims of the disaster were the 11 workers who lost their lives, fisheries, tourism, marine flora and fauna, as well as various bird species that were severely affected. (Bukharitsin, 2022).

Figure 5: Oil spill caused by an offshore platform accident (NASA Earth Observatory, 2010)

Remote sensing provides key data for analyzing oil spill impacts on large, complex coastlines.

3.2. The Norilsk Disaster

On May 29, 2020, a major oil spill incident happened close to the city of Norilsk in Russia. (Sahu & Dutta, 2021). The spill happened because a fuel tank broke down, which caused a large area of water and soil to become polluted. The oil spill was a major industrial accident that realised 20,000 tons of fuel into the nearby Daldykan and Ambarnaya rivers. Figure 6 shows the area polluted by the oil spill from the fuel reservoir (Sahu & Dutta, 2021).

Figure 6: Satellite image of the area polluted by the oil spill from the fuel reservoir 0

4. IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF DIGITAL IMAGES

The significance of an image is considerably more complex and has a broader application than a photograph. Images provide useful information about changes in land and objects on it. In the satellite image of the area affected by the oil spill (Figure 6), spatial, radiometric, and spectral enhancement was performed using the MATLAB software package.

4.1. Spatial Improvement of Digital Image Quality

Spatial improvement of image quality refers to improving the quality of the visual presentation and emphasizing the desired information. As part of the spatial improvement of digital image quality in the MATLAB program, image filtering and edge enhancement of objects were performed.

Figures 7 and 8 show images corrupted by Gaussian, Poisson, salt-and-pepper, and multispectral noise, each affecting 10% of the image area.

Figure 7: Image affected by Gaussian noise (left) and Poisson noise (right). The images were processed in MATLAB.

Figure 8: Image affected by salt-and-pepper noise (left) and multispectral noise (right). The images were processed in MATLAB.

5. CONCLUSION

Remote sensing methods are used for the creation of orthophoto maps and charts derived from generated satellite images of a particular area, enabling efficient data collection along with a clear overview of the entire study area. Remote sensing can be viewed as a multidisciplinary system of “tools” that can be applied to define, analyze, and solve problems and challenges encountered in emergency situations. The ability to obtain accurate and timely information can assist in resolving field situations. By combining remote sensing methods, it is possible to create a pseudo-realistic representation of the entire situation and make strategic and tactical decisions quickly in accordance with the presented challenges.

In hazardous or hard-to-reach areas remote sensing enables data collection. The development of SMOS and other satellite Earth observation systems is of great importance for understanding the condition of seawater and oceans. By using images obtained through remote sensing, it is possible to successfully monitor and analyze water conditions, water movements, as well as track and assess water pollution from an ecological perspective. Further processing of satellite images, for example using software packages like MATLAB, allows for digital image processing. There are various digital image processing techniques, and images processed in this way are more suitable for use in specific fields. Although remote sensing is an effective tool for gathering data about the Earth's surface, it faces numerous limitations such as limited spatial and spectral resolution, atmospheric effects, complexity of data interpretation, and dependence on weather conditions and the availability of quality satellite images.

Recently, remote sensing has been rapidly advancing and developing, both in its methods and the technology used, so even greater applications can be expected in the future.

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